

INFLUENCE OF MULTICULTURAL FACTORS ON INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY

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ABSTRACT

Innovations are the phenomenon of globalizing, dynamic and highly competitive markets of goods, services and ideas. Open innovations cross the borders of companies, of countries and of continents and because of it are regarded as cross-cultural process. Georgia's wide-scale integration into global innovation networks supposes the development of cross-cultural competencies for Georgia society. The knowledge and understanding at least, and possibly, the adoption of cultural values of the nations – global innovation leaders - are important.

Keywords: Georgia, innovations, borders of companies, cultural factors, technological progress.

Introduction

In the era of globalization, innovative development is considered the main source of economic progress for any country. Georgia's entry into the world economic system, increasing the country's competitiveness is impossible without the development of technologies and the production of innovative products. If we consider the experience of the "Asian tigers", we can conclude that the forerunner of their "economic leap" is not only an open, liberal economy, but also a deeply thought-out and progressive innovation policy. Orientation towards the development of industries characterized by rapid economic returns (for example, tourism) does not provide an opportunity to obtain long-term economic effects and correct, targeted distribution of investments. In a number of countries of the world, which are characterized by high rates of economic growth and the growing dynamics of GDP per capita, scientific areas take a priority place.

The level of innovation development in Georgia

As evidenced by the country's low level of global competitiveness, Georgia does not have a high level of

innovative development. The reasons for this should be sought in the unsystematic reforms carried out in recent years, which resulted in the systematic destruction of the country's innovative potential. As a result of a completely immature privatization policy, dozens of research institutes were alienated, which led to a paucity of applied and fundamental research and to the technological degradation of the country. Under these conditions, the country actually remained dependent on income from the service sector. The export potential is dominated by agricultural products, and tourism is considered a progressive industry that is not sufficient to maintain the country's monetary stability, which is why the local currency, the GEL experiences significant fluctuations. The immature state policy in the field of innovation does not make it possible to predict the economic development of the country in the long term.

Georgia's position in the global innovation index is unfavorable (see figure 1). According to the 2021 indicators, the country's ranking has dropped 15 positions to 63rd.

Figure 1. Georgia's position in the global innovation index from 2015 to 2021.

Source: www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_gii_2021.pdf

Researchers cite the economic crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic as one of the additional reasons for the deterioration of the global innovation index. Georgia's rating has deteriorated in 5 out of 7 categories of this index. These are: market development, where the country ranked from 15th to 39th place; business development took 70th place out of 79th; creativity—from 58th to 68th; and infrastructure development—from 72nd to 81st. Knowledge and technology indicators also deteriorated. In Russia, Ukraine and Georgia are ranked 46th, 37th, and 63rd respectively, while in 2020 this figure was 46th, 47th, and 48th respectively.

The analysis shows that Georgia's score has deteriorated by 15 points [www.wipo.int_2021.pdf]. In the category of institutions, the country occupies a leading position in terms of the ease of starting a business. However, depending on the level of business development, there is a lack of scientific cooperation between higher education institutions and the private sector and a low level of cluster development.

The following factors have a negative impact on the development of the innovation economy in Georgia:

- ❖ low level of demand for innovative products;
- ❖ low qualification of scientific personnel;
- ❖ underdevelopment of the technological market;
- ❖ low level of financing of science from the state budget;
- ❖ underdeveloped network of informal investors;
- ❖ low prevalence of crowdfunding as a fundraising tool;
- ❖ lack of inventions, etc.

The results of the analysis of the global innovation index allow us to see stagnation in the country. Innovative opportunities play an important role in the development of the economy, so an integrated and integrated approach to solving problems in this area is needed.

Innovation is usually understood as technological innovation. However, they are only part of the overall innovation process, and, as practice shows, this process cannot be successful without considering cultural factors. The innovation process in a globalized business environment, unlike the traditional one, requires a broader and more comprehensive consideration of innovation. A comprehensive, multidisciplinary, and interdisciplinary approach to this process allows us to answer many questions that are relevant given the realities of Georgia. The problem of technical innovation today goes beyond the development of new products; the focus is shifting to issues such as business model, corporate structure, value chain creation, service, brand, and customer experience [Andrew, 2009, p. 8].

The well-known researcher M. McKeown [McKeown, 2008, p. 341] presents the following sequence of the innovation process:

1. generation of ideas;
2. dissemination;
3. practical implementation;
4. creation of news

In the context of globalization, several organizations can participate in the innovation process. Accordingly, innovation carried out by one organization is local, and innovation carried out by several organizations is global. In modern conditions, international companies are characterized by a high level of cooperation and coordination in the field of innovation and are focused on global innovation, which is an important source of technological progress and the strength of the country's economy.

Thus, global innovation can be seen as a phenomenon characteristic of developed countries with modern market conditions, characterized by a high degree of integration and globalization. For Georgia's part, it is not among such countries, so it does not participate in the global innovation process. For this reason, the possibility of obtaining income from this most important factor is limited. It is also clear that this reason determines the peripheral place of Georgia in the technological development of the world.

Chesbrough [Chesbrough, 2006, p. 403] rightly believes that global innovation largely "depends on the development of intermediate markets for ideas and technologies." In Georgia, such an intermediary market is not only not developed but not even formed. Business models of open innovations are determined by such objective factors as globalization of markets and global competition; shortening of the product life cycle; complexity of the creation of new technologies (accordingly, an increase in costs and risks); development of markets for technologies; personnel and financial solutions.

In modern conditions, innovations are born and developed in a different cultural environment. Consequently, the impact of culture on the innovation process is becoming increasingly important.

Cultural aspect of innovation

In innovation, along with the technical component, it is necessary to take into account its cultural origin since it is culture that determines the specifics and features of the innovation process. The success of the global innovation process requires taking into account the multicultural characteristics of nations, a correct understanding of the dominant function of the state, and the study of religious approaches to innovation. Harrison studied the cultural characteristics of Central America and the Caribbean. Scientists came to the conclusion that poverty and injustice prevailing in these countries have deep cultural roots, and religion played an important role in this process as the most important determinant of culture. Some religions focus more on personal responsibility, entrepreneurship, education, and trust than others. In terms of democracy, welfare, and the rule of law, Protestant societies are far ahead of Catholic ones. Japan, Singapore, South Korea, Taiwan, and China have achieved transformative economic growth [Harrison 2006, p.134]. The high level of economic development of the Nordic countries can be explained by the religious factor, which is substantiated in the work of Max Weber: "The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism" (Weber, 2002). The Church Reformation, inspired by the ideas of Calvinism and Lutheranism, led to a strong and progressive impetus

for the European economy. Harrison, who connects capitalism with democracy and freedom, also highlights the role of the Orthodox Church, which promoted anti-capitalist tendencies in Orthodox countries, which, in turn, had a negative impact on the innovative develop-

ment of these regions [Harrison, 2006. p. 108]. The scientist believes that as a result of cultural transmission over time, it is possible to develop the culture of a separate nation, which in turn will lead to political pluralism and economic progress. Figure 1 depicts the most important tools for these changes:

Figure 1: Cultural Change Tools according to Harrison

Source: Harrison L., (2006) *The Central Liberal Truth: How Politics Can Change a Culture and Save It from Itself*. Oxford University Press, 2006. -288 pp.

1. Education contributes to the development of democratic and entrepreneurial values.
2. Religious reform promotes the transformation of cultural values.
3. By improving the upbringing of children, it contributes to the formation of cultural values.

Among the cultural factors of technological progress, the British researcher Gelade singles out an open intellectual environment, intellectual autonomy, and social equality [Gelade, 2008, p. 712]. American researcher Shane [Shane, 1993, p. 51] notes that attitudes towards uncertainty (as a willingness to take risks and changes), individualism (as autonomy, independence, and freedom) and the lack of power distance (as the opposite of hierarchy and authoritarianism) are associated with the high innovativeness of nations. "The nation's pace of innovation is determined more by fundamental forces than by economic conditions. Social change may be needed to make a less innovative society more innovative" [Shane, 1993, p. 38]. According to S. Sheman, the development of a country is determined by such cultural factors as openness to foreign ideas and the desire

of the nation to cooperate with foreigners [Sheman, 2009, p.178]. According to L. Harrison, "some cultures are more prone to progress, while others are not." and antiprogress. Factors of culture are combined into 4 groups: "Perception of the world", "Values", "Economic behavior", and "Social behavior".

We can say that Georgian culture is resistant to innovations; it opposes progress. The basic legal, economic, and democratic conditions of the country do not meet the requirements of the cultural transformation of the country and the formation of an innovative economy.

Culture includes abstract and material elements. Abstract elements include values, norms, and ideas. All components of culture are interconnected. For example, S. Sheman believes that democracy is impossible in a country where GDP per capita does not exceed \$10,000 [Sheman, 2009, p.71].

J. Mowen [Mowen, 1995, p. 702] points to the relationship between culture, the level of social welfare and public institutions. The scientist created a three-dimensional culture matrix (see Figure 2):

Figure 2. Three-dimensional matrix of event culture.

Source: Mowen J., Consumer Behavior. 4-th ed. Macmillan Publishing Co., 1995. - 862 pp.

1) Individualism, achievements, informativeness, equality, progress, and materialism are cultural values associated with scientists.

2) in the material environment: economic development, geographical features, natural resources, technical/scientific level;

3) in the institutional/social environment: political, religious, business subculture.

In order to intensify the participation of Georgian businesses in global innovations and to overcome multicultural barriers, it is necessary to:

1. Establishment of an innovative market and the establishment of institutional conditions for its growth in Georgia.

2. Establishment of the Institute of Innovation Intermediaries in the country, with this function delegated to the Innovation and Technology Agency.

3. Implementation of the principles of cultural relativism in the field of global innovation.

4. Introduction and active promotion of the concept of cultural tolerance and respect for other cultures among the population.

5. Internationalization of education and business; science; and protection of openness principles.

6. Promotion of innovative values; provision of material and moral support for scientific innovators.

7. Establishment of institutional, legal, and financial frameworks to encourage innovative business in the country.

The implementation of these and other measures will allow Georgia to move into the category of innovative countries from among non-innovative countries, which in turn can become the starting point for the country's economic development.

Conclusion

Innovation is the result of the globalization of goods, services, and ideas, coupled with the development of dynamic and highly competitive markets. Global innovations cross the borders of countries and continents and are therefore strongly influenced by the cultural context. The large-scale integration of Georgia into global innovation networks implies an increase in the intercultural competencies of Georgian society. In

this context, it is important to study and analyze the cultural values that have led Western countries to innovative progress.

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THE QUALITY OF LIQUID FUELS OFFERED IN THE TRADE NETWORK OF POPOVO CITY, BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is to study the quality of liquid fuels offered in the trade network of Popovo city, Bulgaria. The color of liquid fuels is inherent and characteristic, but different hues are observed in motor gasolines, probably due to the presence of artificial additives, dissolved resins or ethyl liquids. The diesel fuels sold from „B“, „C“ and „E“ are cloudy and they are found to have comparatively lower mobility than the others. The presence of opalescence or the content of mechanical impurities in gasoline and diesel fuels is not observed. Gasoline samples taken from „E“ and „D“ are substandard due to their increased density. The diesel fuels offered by „A“, „D“ and „E“ are non-standard, due to their density not being consistent with the standardized norms. The obtained flame temperature of the diesel fuels is in accordance with the regulatory requirements. Gasoline and diesel fuels do not contain water-soluble acids and bases, with the exception of „E“ brand diesel fuel.

Keywords: quality, liquid fuels, quality of liquid fuels.

Introduction

In the context of the growing requirements for fuels, including those related to their impact on the environment, the question of the quality of liquid fuels is becoming more and more relevant. The quality of liquid fuels is the subject of compliance between their quality indicators in relation to standard requirements. The fuels that are produced and offered on the market in Bulgaria must meet the standards adopted in the European Union, which set stricter requirements than the previously existing national standards until the country's accession to the EU [1].

The quality of liquid fuels is one of the key factors that have an impact on engine performance. Particular attention when updating quality standards is paid to the environmental characteristics of fuels, including properties such as sulfur content, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and other pollutants found in diesel and gasoline. The entire set of properties of liquid fuels that determine their quality can be divided into three groups - physico-chemical, operational and technical. Physical and chemical properties characterize the state of liquid

fuels and their composition (density, viscosity, heat capacity, thermal conductivity, electrical conductivity, fractional composition, etc.). The second group contains all operational properties of liquid fuels that ensure the reliability and efficiency of the operation of engines, machines and mechanisms, such as the octane/cetane number of liquid fuels. The technical properties of liquid fuels are combined in a third group. They are not related to their use, but are manifested in the processes of storage and transportation, such as flame and ignition temperature. These fuel quality requirements are subject to analysis and testing in petrochemical laboratories and are determined to be the most important in terms of vehicle engine performance and durability, as well as emissions [1,2,3,4].

The evaluation of the quality is done by comparing the values of the quality indicators of the liquid fuels with base values from the regulated normative requirements. In the Ordinance on the requirements for the quality of liquid fuels, the conditions, order and manner of their control are reflected in tables that note the indicators necessary to assess the level of quality of the tested products, the reference values that they must